

GREEN SCENT

SMART CITIZEN EDUCATION
FOR A GREEN FUTURE

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D1.4 - GreenSCENT Competence Framework Use Case

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Deliverable coordinator	Miroslav Vujcic miroslav.vujcic@dgt.uns.ac.rs
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1. Document Info

1.1. Authors

Author name	Organization Acr.	E-mail
Miroslav Vujcic	UNSPMF	miroslav.vujcic@dgt.uns.ac.rs
Biljana Basarin	UNSPMF	biljana.basarin@dgt.uns.ac.rs
Alessandro Pollini	UNINETT	alessandro.pollini@uninettunouniversity.net

1.2. Contributors

Contributor name	Organization Acr.	E-mail
Ugljesa Stankov	UNSPMF	ugljesa.stankov@dgt.uns.ac.rs

1.3. Reviewers

Reviewer name	Organization Acr.	E-mail
Manfred Mudelsee	CRA	mudelsee@climate-risk-analysis.com
Gian Andrea Giacobone	UNINETT	gianandrea.giacobone@uninettunouniversity.net

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Editor address data	Name: Miroslav Vujcic Partner: Faculty of sciences, University of Novi Sad UNSPMF Address: Trg Dositeja Obradovica 3, Novi Sad, Serbia Phone: +381631155234 Email: miroslav.vujcic@dgt.uns.ac.rs
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Index

1. Introduction	5
2. Showcase example: Climathon	6
2.1. Climathon Use Case Description	6
2.2. GreenSCENT Competence Framework	8
2.3. GreenSCENT Skill Cards	8
2.4. GreenSCENT Climathon Training Kit	11
2.5. Instructional Design Implementation	12
2.5.1. Planning the structure	12
2.5.2. Executing the step-by-step process	12
2.6. Learning Assessment	13
2.6.1. Learning performance evaluation	13
2.6.2. EU Certification Process example for advanced level	15
1 Scope	15
2 Requirements for competence	16
2.1 Competence Profile	16
2.2 Knowledge and skill requirements	16
2.2.1 Unit 1 (Abbrev.U1)	16
2.2.2 Unit 2 (Abbrev.U2)	16
2.2.3 Unit 3 (Abbrev. U3)	16
2.2.4 Unit 4 (Abbrev. U4)	16
2.2.5 Unit 5 (Abbrev. U5)	16
2.2.6 Unit 6 (Abbrev. U6)	17
2.2.7 Unit 7 (Abbrev. U7)	17
3 Requirements for admission to the examination	17
4 Multiple-Choice Exam	17
5 Evaluation Criteria	17
5.1 Multiple-Choice Exam	17
5.2 Overall assessment and examination repetition	17
6 Issue and validity of certificates	17
7 Recertification	17
7.1 Criteria for renewal of the certificate	18
7.2 Issue of the certificate	18
7.3 Deadlines	18
2.6.3. Learning questions for the European Certification	18
2.7. Climathon Use Case in practice: two case studies	44
2.7.1. Secondary Education	44
2.7.2. Higher Education institution	46
3. References	49

1. Introduction

This document presents the deliverable D1.4 GreenSCENT Competence Framework Use Case. The deliverable aims to report a complete showcase of the training and demonstration activities implemented during the pilot activities, representing a tangible example of the final GreenSCENT instructional design framework.

The use case description outlines all the necessary steps to define the required competencies, educational levels, and assessment methods needed to address an educational challenge in the Green Deal area of Climate Change, as outlined in the GreenSCENT Competence Framework.

The document is structured as follows:

- The first section represents a general description of the climate change showcase related to , named Climathon.
- The second section outlines the specific competencies from the GreenSCENT Competence Framework with the Climathon activity focusing on addressing the Climate Change.
- The third section describes the selection of the skill cards used during the Climathon use case.
- The fourth section presents the step by step implementation of instructional design for conducting the educational activities on Climate Change, starting with the sustainable challenge and ending with the final expected results.
- The fifth section describes the learning performance evaluation methodology and certification adopted to evaluate the learners' performance.
- The last section describes the implementation of Instructional Design in two specific use cases related to secondary and higher education institutions.

2. Showcase example: Climathon

2.1. Climathon Use Case Description

Description

The expression “Climathon” is a combination of the words “Hackathon” (a joint offline or online coding and analysis event) and “climate”. The Climathon showcase represents a GreenSCENT educational experience focusing on the Green Deal area of Climate Change. The use case is a high-level online course in climate time series analysis that is specifically tailored to the needs of students, researchers, and professionals who wish to upscale their knowledge on essential combinations of disciplines (climate change and time series analysis) but have had little exposure to in-depth statistical teaching so far or learn new statistical techniques.

his course focuses on basic univariate concepts, such as trends and extremes, aimed for easy accessibility for students early in their careers. The online version emerged in response partly to the COVID-19 situation (which started in 2020) but also to the general upward trend in the need for electronic high-level quality education.

The course provides carefully designed, recorded, and edited videos. Participants can watch the videos repeatedly and take breaks as needed. They will also receive and can study the delivered course slides again.

The use case also provides daily chat meetings via a video platform over the entire course duration, allowing participants to prepare questions beforehand and receive extensive responses.

Finally, an individual feedback period of two months post-course (via email and, possibly, online meetings) preserves the interactive mode of joint data analysis. It allows learners to explore real applications in depth.

Climate change Impact

For living systems on Earth – plants, animals, humans, and society – climate change means a change in the boundary conditions. Life may be able to adapt to changes in the climatic variables of temperature and precipitation, and indeed, it has done so during evolution over the past few billion years. However, the speed of recent climate change since the start of industrialisation in the second half of the 18th century may be beyond the capacity of many systems to adapt.

The physical science base (IPCC, 2021) is unequivocal that the main driver of recent climate change is the anthropogenic increase in greenhouse gas concentrations in the Earth's atmosphere. In addition to the unprecedented speed of recent climate change, it is the fact that this change has taken us into new territory in the state space of the climate. The current atmospheric carbon dioxide concentration level of well over 400 parts per million has not been reached for at least the last eight hundred thousand years, as indicated by the ice core archive (Lüthi et al., 2008; CenCO2PIP, 2023). This uncharted territory, combined with the complexity of the inter-connected climate system, means that future climate is challenging to predict and that surprising climate behaviour and impacts will inevitably accompany us into the future.

Climate change is one part of environmental change. Other parts are, among many others, increasing pollution, biodiversity loss, and habitable land reduction. It is clear that ecological changes have a strong socio-economic dimension and can threaten humans and other lives on Earth dangerously.

Educational Role

From a rational, scientific point of view, it is evident that mitigation and adaptation policies, such as the European Green Deal and similar programmes on other continents, are essential to maintaining a sustainable human life on Earth. These policies will affect the daily lives and work of this and the next generations. What will it take to make mitigation and adaptation work? It requires two ingredients. First, there must be the moral will to embark on the various tasks and to stay on the course for a long time, that is, a few decades. Another reason not to despair is behavioural change. In the GreenSCENT project, we are looking at the second ingredient through education. We think that its definition is quite broad because learning never stops. Therefore, the project deals with different levels of traditional educational formats, From the first classes at school to researchers at universities and other higher education institutions.

Using the United Nations sustainability framework, the Climathon addresses Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4, quality education, and SDG 13, climate action. The overall aim of education provided by the Climathon events is to teach participants the power of quantitative, rational, theory- and data-driven approaches to understanding the climate challenge. Popper (1959), in his Logic of Scientific Discovery, showed that quantitative methods are more useful to qualitative ones because they give researchers more options to test and reject hypotheses to criticise elements of climate theories – falsifiability as a criterion of science. The logic of testing hypotheses and quantifying climate parameters based on data: this is the rational aspect. Sometimes, we climate teachers deliberately allow “irrational aspects” to enter the educational arena by stressing the role of creativity and intuition in formulating new hypotheses and theories. Still, this education is best delivered “offline”, from the teacher to student in personal contact. As the Climathon events had a solid online component, the opportunities to teach irrational aspects were reduced, and the focus was put on many selected climate data analysis tools.

Target

The participants for HEIs are professors, postdocs, and PhD and university students. The participants in schools are pupils at a later stage of their school career (minimum age about 15 years, minimum school year about final or final minus 1). The procedure to recruit participants from HEIs is via CRA's system:

1. adoption of long internal email lists;
2. distribution to specific newsgroups in climate and environmental sciences, ecology, geosciences, physics, mathematics, and statistics; and
3. posting on professional social media (i.e., LinkedIn). Interested participants complete a registration form sent to CRA.

The event is open to EU citizens. The maximum number of participants per event is 20. The procedure for recruiting participants from educational environments through the schools themselves is as follows: school heads or teachers directly approach pupils or make school-internal advertisements.

Ethical Issues

The primary issue is guaranteeing the privacy of participants. This is in response to the EU's GDPR. For participants from HEIs, this is achieved via information and the request for agreement in the Climathon registration form. For school participants (i.e., pupils below 18), privacy is achieved via information and the request for completed consent forms by parents or legal guardians.

Impact

The impact of the Climathon is rooted in the participants' abilities to perform basic science:

- source of data,
- analysis,
- uncertainties,
- interpretation.

These abilities will permeate (1) the various fields of scientific applications the researchers work in (for participants from HEIs) or (2) the various fields of study that the pupils will take up after their school careers (for participants from schools).

2.2. GreenSCENT Competence Framework

The Climathon course is based on specific competencies — knowledge, skills and attitudes — described in the GreenSCENT Competence Framework (1st release) (Deliverable D1.1) that are addressed during its educational activity:

- Competence 1.1 Climate Change Scientific Literacy
- Competence 1.3 Know-how problem solving
- Competence 4.3 Risk management vulnerability and impact analysis
- Competence 6.2 Monitoring the speed of phenomena and their adaptation.

2.3. GreenSCENT Skill Cards

The Skill Cards that the Climathon course addresses are the following:

EQF level 1

- 1.2. Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy Knowledge 1 Understands that climate change is inevitable and that adaptation is needed to be able to preserve a functioning economy without harming nature
- 1.3. Know-how problem-solving Knowledge 1 Knows that action for climate change need clear identification of a problem and well-defined plan
- 1.3. Know-how problem-solving Skills 1 Can identify existing issues in the context of climate change
- 2,1 Climate Change cross-cultural practice Knowledge 1 Knows that environmental concerns are not equally distributed across cultures
- 2,1 Climate Change cross-cultural practice Skills 1 Identifies what observed impacts of climate change may vary regionally and seasonally
- 2.2. Collaboration among diverse stakeholders Knowledge 1 Knows the existence of many parties that share the same values for climate change but also might have diverse interests
- 2.2. Collaboration among diverse stakeholders Skills 1 Can identify diverse stakeholders and their interests
- 2.3. Climate-informed change management Knowledge 1 Has basic knowledge about climate change historically and nowadays
- 2.3. Climate-informed change management Skills 1 Identifies the features of climate change nowadays
- 3.1. Climate change communication Knowledge 1 Knows different communication channels for climate change
- 3.1. Climate change communication Skills 1 Can describe a simple transmission model of communication, comprised of a messenger who transmits a message through particular channels to specific audiences
- 3.2. Various scientific areas and industrial cross-sector cooperation Knowledge 1 Understands that climate change issue requires broad spectra of different areas of knowledge
- 3.2. Various scientific areas and industrial cross-sector cooperation Skills 1 Can describe the scientific and industrial areas and their possible collaborations towards climate change action goals
- 4.1. Strategy & Planning for an adaptation Knowledge 1 Smarter adaptation: adaptation actions must be informed by robust data and risk assessment tools that are available to all – from families building homes, businesses in coastal regions and farmers planning their crops
- 4.2. Solution Design Knowledge 1 Ecology for buildings
- 4.2. Solution Design Skills 1 Ecology
- 4.3. Risk Management, Vulnerability & Impact Analysis Knowledge 1 Identifying existing weaknesses caused by anthropic activities that affect lands and cities and evidence, focus and monitor the threat that causes harm
- 5.1. Prevention and preparedness actions Knowledge 1 Future impact of climatic changes upon the frequency and severity of disasters
- 6.1. Adaptation knowledge creation Knowledge 1 Net-zero transition
- 6.2. Monitoring the speed of phenomena and their adaptation Skills 1 Difference from slow-onset and sudden-onset event's impact
- 7.2. Local adaptation action and nature-based solution Knowledge 1 Conserving existing wetlands to prevent greenhouse gas emissions. Restorative agriculture and regrowing clear-cut forests actively remove CO2 from the atmosphere
- 7.2. Local adaption action and nature-based solution Skills 1 Increase awareness of biodiversity.

EQF level 2

- 1.2. Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy Knowledge 2 Knows the consequences of clearing forests, the increase of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, nuclear waste and the use of genetically modified organisms
- 1.2. Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy Skills 2 Can personally contribute to energy and water savings as well as reduce air pollution and extinction of plants and animals by preserving local biodiversity
- 1.3. Know-how problem-solving Knowledge 2 Is informed about the local and international policy frameworks to reduce climate change due to human impact
- 1.3. Know-how problem-solving Skills 2 Identifies a problem, comes to a clear, precise, and complete understanding of the situation
- 2,1 Climate Change cross-cultural practice Knowledge 2 Is aware that many societies prefer economic and political stability over environmental security
- 2.2. Collaboration among diverse stakeholders Knowledge 2 Understands that the complexity of climate change depends on the impacts of climate change adaptation must draw together solutions that span social, economic and political boundaries
- 2.2. Collaboration among diverse stakeholders Skills 2 Can explain the importance of diverse parties' collaboration
- 2.3. Climate-informed change management Knowledge 2 Has advanced knowledge of climate change during history and nowadays
- 2.3. Climate-informed change management Skills 2 Identifies the features of climate change nowadays and can suggest how these effects can be reduced
- 3.1. Climate change communication Knowledge 2 Understands that climate change communication should be adapted to the dynamic and complex audience
- 3.1. Climate change communication Skills 2 Is ready to hear opposing messages through an ever-growing number and complexity of channels to diverse audiences who have their own pre-existing beliefs, attitudes and values and who actively interpret and construct their meanings from the messages they receive
- 3.2. Various scientific areas and industrial cross-sector cooperation Knowledge 2 Knows how each scientific area and industrial sector can contribute to climate change reduction
- 3.2. Various scientific areas and industrial cross-sector cooperation Skills 2 Can draw a strategy of how several areas could achieve a climate change action goal
- 4.1. Strategy & Planning for an adaptation Knowledge 2 Faster adaptation: The effects of climate change are already being felt, and so we must adapt more quickly and comprehensively. We are developing and rolling out adaptation solutions to help reduce climate-related risk, increase climate protection, and safeguard the availability of freshwater.

EQF level 3

- 1.2. Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy Knowledge 3 Awareness of how climate change and technologies shape our material, intellectual, and cultural environments
- 1.2. Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy Skills 3 Identify climate change issues, explain phenomena scientifically and use scientific evidence
- 1.3. Know-how problem-solving Knowledge 3 Basic understanding of climate change science
- 1.3. Know-how problem-solving Skills 3 Identifies useful and missing data, can foresee the trends from data
- 2.1. Climate Change cross-cultural practice Knowledge 3 Understanding that the security of the environment should be a personal goal
- 2.1. Climate Change cross-cultural practice Skills 3 Can identify different national and international regulations to mitigate climate change
- 2.1. Climate Change cross-cultural practice Skills 3 Works alone and cooperates to reduce gas emissions, air and water pollution
- 2.2. Collaboration among diverse stakeholders Knowledge 3 Understands that collaborations can be created with potential long-term benefits, including ensuring the cost-effectiveness of planned actions and helping to address and resolve competing priorities
- 2.2. Collaboration among diverse stakeholders Skills 3 Gets involved in a non-profit organisation

- 2.3. Climate-informed change management Knowledge 3 Understanding that society must adapt to a changed climate
- 2.3. Climate-informed change management Skills 3 Shows personally adapted and changed personal lifestyle for climate change
- 3.1. Climate change communication Knowledge 3 Has the different levels of knowledge, economic, political, and scientific, to communicate the climate change
- 3.1. Climate change communication Skills 3 Developed ability to tackle the climate change calls for bridging the science/policy/civil society gap
- 3.2. Various scientific areas and industrial cross-sector cooperation Knowledge 3 Understands the scientific and industry cooperation importance
- 3.2. Various scientific areas and industrial cross-sector cooperation Skills 3 Can tackle the issues and barriers occurring in the cross-industry cooperation process for climate change
- 4.3. Risk Management, Vulnerability & Impact Analysis Skills 3 Climatic and non-climatic issues and stresses environmental change and consumption levels, and their integration with other drivers
- 5.1. Prevention and preparedness actions Skills 3 Community-based disaster preparedness and mitigation programmes
- 6.1. Adaptation knowledge creation Knowledge 3 Mitigation efforts to lower greenhouse gas emissions
- 6.2. Monitoring the speed of phenomena and their adaptation Knowledge 3 Conceptual background of approaches to address loss and damage associated with slow onset events
- 7.1. Macro fiscal policy dedicated to climate change Knowledge 3 Climate change mitigation requires a transition in the structure of economic activity on a massive scale.

EQF level 4

- 1.2. Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy Knowledge 4 Understanding of the practical characteristic features of climate change as a form of human knowledge and inquiry
- 1.2. Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy Skills 4 Support the use of factual information and rational explanations and express the need for logical and careful processes in drawing conclusions
- 1.3. Know-how problem-solving Knowledge 4 Understanding of scientific consensus on climate change and potential impacts
- 1.3. Know-how problem-solving Skills 4 Highlights key problem/solution components, suggests concrete, original, and practical solutions spontaneously
- 2.1. Climate Change cross-cultural practice Knowledge 4 Understanding that for cross-cultural collaboration, the psychological barriers must be reduced (e.g. distrust, belief in external control, individualism-collectivism)
- 2.1. Climate Change cross-cultural practice Skills 4 Can discuss scientific consensus with people who hold diverse beliefs about climate change
- 2.2. Collaboration among diverse stakeholders Knowledge 4 Understands that private companies can provide technological solutions and make them more affordable for solving problems
- 2.3. Climate-informed change management Knowledge 4 Understands the appropriate use of system tools such as biodiversity assessments and product life assessments
- 2.3. Climate-informed change management Skills 4 Advocates for the appropriate use of system tools such as biodiversity assessments and product life assessments
- 2.3. Climate-informed change management Skills 4 Evaluate risks in the enterprise
- 3.1. Climate change communication Knowledge 4 Has enough scientific knowledge to convince the climate change deniers
- 3.1. Climate change communication Skills 4 Ability to gather data for effective interdisciplinary communication
- 3.2. Various scientific areas and industrial cross-sector cooperation Knowledge 4 Is informed what technologies and the different regions of knowledge and practice can be helpful for climate change action
- 3.2. Various scientific areas and industrial cross-sector cooperation Skills 4 Can reach an agreement between conflicting parts and offer alternative solutions
- 4.1. Strategy & Planning for an Adaptation Knowledge 4 Environmental sensors
- 5.1. Prevention and preparedness actions Knowledge 4 Technologies for first responders
- 5.1. Prevention and preparedness actions Skills 4 Assess the Future Impact of Climatic Changes upon the Frequency and Severity of Disasters and the Implications for first response and Preparedness

- 5.2. Resilience technologies, managing the consequences Knowledge 4 Scientific breakthroughs in various domains ranging from technologies, solutions and services: drought-resilient crops, water-saving technologies, satellites for environmental observation, rapid progress in adaptation science and climate analytics as a basis for state-of-the-art climate information, scaling up of digital tools to take our adaptive capacities to the next level
- 6.1. Adaptation knowledge creation Knowledge 4 Adjust societies to withstand the impacts of climate change
- 6.2. Monitoring the speed of phenomena and their adaptation Knowledge 4 Empirical evidence linking a cluster of slow onset events to human mobility decisions, trajectories and outcomes.

EQF level 5

- 3.2. Various scientific areas and industrial cross-sector cooperation Knowledge 5 Is informed that climate change reduction is not only a scientific problem but also of social sciences and humanities
- 4.1. Strategy & Planning for an Adaptation Knowledge 5 Remote-sensing platforms

2.4. GreenSCENT Climathon Training Kit

Training Kit

The Training Kit to implement the Climathon is made of the following elements:

- Slides Electronic: PDF Climathon course slides (lectures and computer tutorials)
- Data: Electronic, compressed Data for computer tutorials
- Software: Electronic, compressed Software for computer tutorials
- Reading: Material Electronic, PDF Coursebook and homework
- Video Links: Electronic, URLs Climathon video modules, explaining course slides
- Chat Link: Electronic, URLs Climathon, online discussions about videos, lectures and tutorials; also joint data analyses.

Technology

The Climathon required the following technologies for its development as a course:

- database management (Windows™, Grapher™, text-based);
- Fortran programming (Intel™, gfortran);
- graphic design (Indesign™).

These tools have existed in their basic form for years to decades.

The Climathon required the following technologies for its implementation:

- visualisation machines (beamer, screen) for showing the slides;
- calculation machines (computers) to replicate the analyses.

All of these tools have existed in their basic form for decades.

2.5. Instructional Design Implementation

2.5.1. Planning the structure

The protocol to prepare the Climathon activity within the GreenSCENT project is as follows:

1. Define your scientific learning sub-disciplines from (a) climatology, (b) meteorology and (c) statistical sciences. Set the specific learning objectives you wish to address.

2. Create new or adapt existing learning media to achieve the learning objectives from step (1). The Media formats may include (a) slides, (b) videos, (c) software and (d) online chat platforms:
3. Prepare a list of essential information for participants about objectives, media and preparation.
4. Prepare a list of essential information for teachers about objectives, media, and preparation. Discuss the feasibility and best implementation practices with teachers beforehand. If needed, adapt lists (3) and (4).
5. Configure course details: title, short description and critical dates and times.
6. Define assessment criteria: Outline the requirements for evaluating course contributions. These criteria should be aligned with your course objectives (1).
7. Set incentives: Determine the rewards or prizes for successful participants. These can generate motivation and attract a broader audience.

2.5.2. Executing the step-by-step process

The three steps presented in the GreenSCENT Instructional Model (Deliverable D1.5) describe the educational experience provided by the Climathon.

Climathon encourages participants to investigate a specific challenge within the Climate Change area, explore it through practical data analysis exercises, and then document it by developing a data report as a tangible result of the proposed learning experience. The overall timescale of the learning activities is set on 3 days.

1) Provide the assignment

Assign learners the tasks of a particular challenge in sustainability that addresses the learning objectives defined for the Climathon. Provide them with educational material (such as a scientific paper) that supports gaining new knowledge and competencies before the practical activity.

The Climathon course requires that participants become knowledgeable of the peer-reviewed literature on the science of climate change. Besides the theoretical foundations of the statistical and time-series analytical frameworks, the cornerstone of the course is to supply participants with hands-on exercises to increase their problem-solving abilities.

The Climathon course for GreenSCENT emphasises climate extremes (taught in Chapter 6 of the course book, Mudelsee M, 2014, Climate Time Series Analysis, 2nd edition, Springer, 454 pp) since this aspect has solid socio-economic relevance. Finally, in Chapter 4 of the course book, we deal with trends and assessments of slopes of climate change, that is, the estimation of the speed of climate change, with uncertainty measures.

The educational experience is based on delivering three lectures on Climate Change and data. Learners are required to follow the preparatory lesson before data analysis.

- 1st DAY - Lecture: Climate.
 - 1st Lecture: climate system; climate variables (temperature, precipitation, wind speed); surface-air temperature time series, global; surface-air temperature time series, local (Potsdam, Germany); paleoclimate rainfall time series; proxy variables
 - 2nd Lecture: climate equation; trend component; extreme component; noise component; scientific method; Karl Popper; Plato; first principles of physics; statistical inference
- 2nd DAY - Lecture: Climate Data.
 - Temperature time series; measurement devices; invention of thermometer; daily measurement practices
 - Mean monthly versus mean monthly temperature time series; sample size; leap days; GISTEMP global, monthly-mean, surface-air temperature time series.
- 3rd DAY - Lecture: Climate Data Analysis.
 - Trend component definition; linear trend model. How do we infer linear trend components? Uncertainties
 - Statistical inference. The idea of least-squares trend estimation. Calculation of least squares trend estimates for the GISTEMP series.

2) Launch the challenge

Deliver the instruction of the learning challenge according to the planned design and steps described in the selected GreenSCENT Use Case.

After the theoretical lecture, learners can tackle a specific challenge through a practical activity consisting of data analysis and manipulation.

- 1st DAY - Exercises
 - How do the first principles of physics lead to the climate equation or something else? What is a 90% confidence band? Do you have examples of concepts for complex systems other than climate?
- 2nd DAY - Exercises
 - How many days comprise the time interval from 01/01/1893 to 31/12/2018? Data homogeneity: rural versus urban temperature measurement stations. Data file and text editor. Find the Internet's temperature data for your preferred station (town).
- 3rd DAY - Exercises
 - Software LINFIT. Replication of calculation of least squares trend estimates for the GISTEMP series. Calculate least squares trend estimates for the series from the preferred stations (2nd Day).

3) Require documentation for evaluation

Deliver instruction on organising learners' data and results to develop the final report to complete the education activities.

At the end of the three days, learners are asked to develop a final report on developing nonlinear trend models to interpret their data analysis. The result presentation occurs through a collaborative discussion among the learners.

2.6. Learning Assessment

2.6.1. Learning performance evaluation

The Climathon use case adopts the GreenSCENT Competence Questionnaire and the GreenSCENT Learning Performance Assessment methods to measure learners' learning outcomes, gather educators' opinions, and assess behaviour change.

The GreenSCENT Competence Questionnaire is administered to each learner before and after conducting the practical educational activities. The tool measures automatic biases and attitudes toward environmental actions and themes by using the Brief Implicit Association Test (BIAT), a streamlined version of the Implicit Association Test. If necessary, the questionnaire should be administered in person to guide learners. Completing it takes approximately 20-30 minutes without interruption.

This procedure requires each learner to have a computer to install the Inquisit software and an associated plugin to conduct the test. The learning program must be represented by a specific ID code that can be used to identify the results obtained in that particular educational experience. The exact ID must be recorded to be used again at the end of the learning activity.

The software installation and the procedure description are described in the specific instructions of the questionnaire. This is the link to the tool: <https://mili2nd.eu/z6ec>

While the learning performance assessment process follows the schedule of instructional design research, which is explained as the last stage of the GreenSCENT educational framework presented in D1.5.

Climathon adopts the template for learning performance assessment already presented in deliverable D1.5. It includes 1) a learning performance assessment description and 2) an assessment rubric. Academic and professional educators are responsible for filling the document on both pages for each learner. These pages represent valuable tools to support the evaluation and quantitative assessment of learning performance throughout the demonstrators' activities.

Learning performance assessment is focused on the final product (or artefact) produced by groups of students, and the first page is dedicated to summarising:

- learning objectives and skills cards selected during the pilot (Competences related to Skill Cards – Green Deal Domain, Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes)
- learning activity description (Educational Activity – Challenge and Exploration)
- representation of the product (or artefact) resulting from the work of the learners (report/artefact)

The second page includes the assessment rubric with the details of the learning assessment criteria:

- LC0 - Group Engagement: Group members' active contribution to the activity.
- LC1 - Motivation: Active contribution to the activity.
- LC2 - Novelty: Novelty of scope and role of the artefact
- LC3 - Accuracy: Record evidence appropriate to Objectives and Skills
- LC4 - Elaboration: Explore data to develop informed connections
- LC5 - Presentation: Efficacy of communication

Three levels have been proposed for each criterion: Level 1—Basic, Level 2—Intermediate, and Level 3—Advanced. The evaluation is provided by checking the appropriate score for each criterion.

Considering the Climathon use case, it primarily aims to equip higher education institution (HEI) participants with theoretical knowledge, statistical methodologies, and practical skills necessary for climate data analysis. This training will enhance climate change quantification, improve climate impact assessments (particularly climate extremes), and support informed evaluations of potential climate actions. Additionally, the Climathon provides training to school students to deepen their understanding of climate change's quantitative aspects within the European Green Deal framework.

Pilot	Criteria	LC0			LC1			LC2			LC3			LC4			LC5		
	Education level	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
EA, Greece	High school		x			x			x			x			x				x
RGSMART, Serbia	High school	x				x			x			x			x				x
UNSPMF, Serbia	University			x			x			x			x			x			x

The Climathon pilot was implemented at both high school and university levels. Regarding group engagement (LC0), participation was recorded across all three levels. The platform served primarily as a space for idea sharing, with limited group interaction; however, it allowed teams the flexibility to advance by articulating the merits of alternative ideas through climate change data analysis. As anticipated, the highest engagement level was observed at the university level, where students demonstrated a deeper understanding of climate change issues and strong analytical skills.

Group engagement and motivation (LC1) were closely correlated in the context of Climathon. Students' motivation to contribute actively was strongly linked to group engagement, with both aspects being assessed in a similar way. University students, as expected, exhibited a high level of intrinsic motivation, consistently participating and engaging in meaningful ways. For high school students, motivation levels ranged from basic to intermediate, reflecting a broader variability in their interest and commitment to climate-related topics.

Regarding the novelty (LC2) of artefacts produced by the Climathon in high schools, it functioned primarily as a collection and exploration of existing ideas, providing students with foundational insights into climate change

topics. In contrast, at the university level, it facilitated the development and extension of novel interpretations of climate data, empowering students to apply advanced analytical and statistical skills to generate original insights.

This differentiation aligns with the original goal of Climathon as a pilot—primarily aimed at higher education students and professionals who possess the requisite analytical capabilities to engage deeply with climate data. However, applying Climathon at lower education levels requires further adaptation, exceptionally accommodating students without statistical backgrounds. Tailoring the program for these levels could involve more accessible, hands-on activities that introduce data interpretation skills incrementally, fostering a foundational understanding of climate change analysis while building toward more complex engagement as students' progress.

Accuracy (LC3): In all three Climathon pilots, evidence was recorded that aligned with the objectives and skill levels at three tiers—basic, intermediate, and advanced. This data corresponded closely with group engagement and students' motivation, providing insight into how these factors influenced performance across different levels of expertise.

Similarly, regarding elaboration (LC4), information on climate change data analysis in high schools was primarily drawn from Climathon resources with limited interpretation or evaluation. In contrast, at the university level, Climathon facilitated a more comprehensive approach, allowing students to engage deeply with the data and develop detailed analyses. This distinction highlights the program's capacity to adapt to different educational needs, providing foundational knowledge for high school students while encouraging university students to apply critical thinking and advanced analysis to climate change data.

Despite challenges within the previously mentioned criteria, the efficacy of communication (LC5) in the pilot programs was generally evaluated as clear and consistent. At the university level, presentations were notably polished, and the content was cohesive, contributing to a well-organised information delivery. This clarity and coherence supported students' understanding and engagement, reinforcing the value of structured and effective communication in conveying complex climate change topics.

2.6.2. EU Certification Process example for advanced level

Here the typical schema to structure the certification exam for an advanced level:

1 Scope

This certification scheme specifies the procedure of how the competence of persons in the field of ECCEL – Advanced Level, is being certified by ECQA GmbH.

The certification organisation ECQA GmbH is an Austrian company, which is 60% owned by the non-profit organisation European Certification and Qualification Association (ECQA).

The object of certification is exclusively / solely the competence of natural persons.

The certification is largely based on the principles of the International Standard ISO/IEC 17024:2012-07 Conformity assessment - General requirements for bodies certifying persons.

2 Requirements for competence

2.1 Competence Profile

Individuals certified in accordance with this certification scheme are competent to independently plan and deliver ECCEL – Advanced Level as a service, using appropriate technical tools and applications.

2.2 Knowledge and skill requirements

The increasing need for effective climate change adaptation is reflected in the comprehensive spectrum of

required competencies outlined by the European Green Deal. These competencies, divided into specific areas, highlight not only the technical and scientific capabilities needed but also the importance of cross-disciplinary skills and proactive attitudes. Within the climate change focus area, key competencies include scientific literacy on climate change, adaptation practices, adaptation leadership, and interdisciplinary communication skills. These competencies are essential for effectively addressing today's complex environmental challenges and demand a holistic approach that integrates science, policy, economics, and community practices. Local approaches and nature-based solutions emerge as critical for climate action, emphasising a clear connection between environmental protection and economic and social sustainability. Individuals performing ECCEL – Advanced Level Climate Change must demonstrate competencies as specified in Sections 2.2.1 through 2.2.7.

2.2.1 Unit 1 (Abbrev.U1)

- E1: Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy (EQF3)
- E2: Know-how problem solving (EQF3)

2.2.2 Unit 2 (Abbrev.U2)

- E1: Climate change cross-cultural practice (EQF3)
- E2: Collaboration among diverse stakeholders (EQF2)
- E3: Climate informed change management (EQF3)

2.2.3 Unit 3 (Abbrev. U3)

- E1: Climate change communication (EQF2)
- E2: Various scientific areas and industrial cross-sector cooperation (EQF2)

2.2.4 Unit 4 (Abbrev. U4)

- E1: Strategy & Planning for an adaptation (EQF4)
- E2: Solution Design (EQF1)

2.2.5 Unit 5 (Abbrev. U5)

- E1: Prevention and preparedness actions (EQF3)

2.2.6 Unit 6 (Abbrev. U6)

- E1: Adaptation knowledge creation (EQF3)
- E2: Monitoring the speed of phenomena and their adaption (EQF1)

2.2.7 Unit 7 (Abbrev. U7)

- E1: Local adaption action and nature based solution (EQF1)

3 Requirements for admission to the examination

Prerequisite for admission to the examination is

- None (although the completion of a recommended training is suggested)

4 Multiple-Choice Exam

The examination is done in writing as a multiple-choice test online. The exam consists of 26 questions, from a pool of more than 57 questions in total, from the seven subject areas as per section 2.2.1 to 2.2.7.

The maximum duration of the written exam is set at 45 min.

5 Evaluation Criteria

5.1 Multiple-Choice Exam

Each question is scored with a maximum of one point each. There are several answer options per question. For each complete exam at least 50% of the total score must be achieved.

5.2 Overall assessment and examination repetition

To pass the overall examination, at least 50% must be achieved.

6 Issue and validity of certificates

The successful evaluation of the initial certification examination, according to section 5, is a prerequisite for the issuance of a certificate.

The certificates are valid for 2 years.

7 Recertification

7.1 Criteria for renewal of the certificate

To renew the certificate, the certificate holder must fulfil the following criteria:

7.1.1 The certificate holder must retake the exam.

7.2 Issue of the certificate

After fulfilling all the criteria, according to 7.1.1, the certificate is renewed for 2 years.

7.3 Deadlines

Recertification must take place before the certificate expires. In exceptional cases, recertification may also take place after expiry of the certificate. In this case, the following conditions apply:

7.3.1 If the recertification takes place after the expiration of the validity of a certificate within a period of maximum 6 months, the recertification shall be carried out in accordance with the criteria and process specified in Section 7.1. Otherwise, an audit to the extent of the initial certification shall be performed in accordance with Section 5.

7.3.2 The validity of the certificate is always based on the date of initial certification. This means that the date of the initial certification is always taken as the starting point, regardless of the recertification date.

2.6.3. Learning questions for the European Certification

According to the topic of Climathon, here are the following questions for passing the certification exam:

Nr.	Topic	Skill	Knowledge/ Skill	EQF	Statement
1.2.	Climate Change	Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy	Knowledge	1	<u>Understands that climate change is inevitable and that the adaptation is needed to be able to preserve functioning economy without harming nature</u>
1.3.	Climate Change	Know-how problem solving	Knowledge	1	<u>Knows that action for climate change need clear identification of a problem and well defined plan</u>
1.3.	Climate Change	Know-how problem solving	Skills	1	<u>Is able to identify existing issues in the context of climate change</u>
2,1	Climate Change	Climate Change Cross-cultural practice	Knowledge	1	<u>Knows that environmental concerns are not equally distributed across cultures</u>
2,1	Climate Change	Climate Change Cross-cultural practice	Skills	1	<u>Identifies what observed impacts of climate change may vary regionally and seasonally</u>
2.2.	Climate Change	Collaboration among diverse stakeholders	Knowledge	1	<u>Knows the existence of many parties that shares the same values for climate change, but also might have diverse interests</u>
2.2.	Climate Change	Collaboration among diverse stakeholders	Skills	1	<u>Is able to identify diverse stakeholders and their interests</u>
2.3.	Climate Change	Climate informed change management	Knowledge	1	<u>Has basic knowledge about the climate change historically and nowadays</u>

2.3.	Climate Change	Climate informed change management	Skills	1	<u>Identifies the features of climate change nowadays</u>
3.1.	Climate Change	Climate change communication	Knowledge	1	<u>Knows different communication channels for climate change</u>
3.1.	Climate Change	Climate change communication	Skills	1	<u>Is able to describe a simple transmission model of communication, comprised of a messenger, who transmits a message through particular channels, to specific audiences</u>
3.2.	Climate Change	Various scientific areas and industrial cross-sector cooperation	Knowledge	1	<u>Understands that climate change issue requires wide spectra of different areas knowledge</u>
3.2.	Climate Change	Various scientific areas and industrial cross-sector cooperation	Skills	1	<u>Can describe the scientific and industrial areas and their possible collaborations towards climate change action goals</u>
4.1.	Climate Change	Strategy & Planning for an adaptation	Knowledge	1	<u>Smarter adaptation: adaptation actions must be informed by robust data and risk assessment tools that are available to all – from families building homes, businesses in coastal regions and farmers planning their crops</u>
4.2.	Climate Change	Solution Design	Knowledge	1	<u>Ecology for buildings</u>
4.2.	Climate Change	Solution Design	Skills	1	<u>Ecology</u>

4.3.	Climate Change	Risk Management , Vulnerability & Impact Analysis	Knowledge	1	Identifying existing weaknesses caused by anthropic activities that affect lands and cities and evidence, focus and monitor the threat that causes harm
					Why is it important to identify weaknesses caused by anthropic activities?
					A) To improve the environment
					B) To harm lands and cities
					C) To ignore the problems
					D) To create more pollution
					Answer: A
5.1.	Climate Change	Prevention and preparedness actions	Knowledge	1	Future impact of climatic changes upon the frequency and severity of disasters
6.1.	Climate Change	Adaptation knowledge creation	Knowledge	1	Net-zero transition
6.2.	Climate Change	Monitoring the speed of phenomena and their adaption	Skills	1	Difference from slow-onset and sudden-onset event's impact
7.2.	Climate Change	Local adaption action and	Knowledge	1	Conserving existing wetlands to prevent greenhouse gas emissions. Restorative agriculture and regrowing clear-cut forests, actively remove CO2 from the atmosphere

		nature based solution			
7.2.	Climate Change	Local adaption action and nature based solution	Skills	1	Increase awareness of biodiversity
EQF level 2					
1.2.	Climate Change	Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy	Knowledge	2	Knows the consequences of clearing forests, the increase of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, nuclear waste and use of genetically modified organisms
1.2.	Climate Change	Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy	Skills	2	Is able to personally contribute to the energy, water savings as well as reduce air pollution , extinction of plants and animals, by preserving local biodiversity
1.3.	Climate Change	Know-how problem solving	Knowledge	2	Is informed about the local and international policy frameworks in order to reduce climate change due to human impact
1.3.	Climate Change	Know-how problem solving	Skills	2	Identifies a problem, comes to a clear, precise, and complete understanding of the situation
2.1	Climate Change	Climate Change Cross-cultural practice	Knowledge	2	Is aware that many societies prefer economic and political stability over environmental security
2.2.	Climate Change	Collaboration among	Knowledge	2	Understands that the complexity of climate change depends on the impacts of climate change

		diverse stakeholders			<u>adaptation that must draw together solutions that span social, economic and political boundaries</u>
2.2.	Climate Change	Collaboration among diverse stakeholders	Skills	2	<u>Is able to explain the importance of diverse parties collaboration</u>
2.3.	Climate Change	Climate informed change management	Knowledge	2	<u>Has advanced knowledge of the climate change during the history and nowadays</u>
2.3.	Climate Change	Climate informed change management	Skills	2	<u>Identifies the features of climate change nowadays and can suggest how these effects can be reduced</u>
3.1.	Climate Change	Climate change communication	Knowledge	2	<u>Understands that climate change communication should be adapted to the dynamical and complex audience</u>
3.1.	Climate Change	Climate change communication	Skills	2	<u>Is ready to hear opposing messages, through an ever-growing number and complexity of channels, to diverse audiences who have their own pre-existing beliefs, attitudes and values, and who actively interpret and construct their own meanings from the messages they receive</u>
3.2.	Climate Change	Various scientific areas and industrial cross-sector cooperation	Knowledge	2	<u>Knows how each scientific area and industrial sector can contribute to the climate change reduction</u>
3.2.	Climate Change	Various scientific areas and industrial	Skills	2	<u>Is able to draw a strategy of how several areas could achieve a climate change action goal</u>

		cross-sector cooperation			
4.1.	Climate Change	Strategy & Planning for an adaptation	Knowledge	2	<u>Faster adaptation: the effects of climate change are already being felt, and so we must adapt more quickly and comprehensively. Developing and rolling out adaptation solutions to help reduce climate-related risk, increase climate protection and safeguard the availability of freshwater.</u>
EQF level 3					
1.2.	Climate Change	Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy	Knowledge	3	<u>Awareness of how climate change and technologies shape our material, intellectual, and cultural environments</u>
1.2.	Climate Change	Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy	Skills	3	<u>Identify climate change issues, explain phenomena scientifically and use scientific evidence</u>
1.3.	Climate Change	Know-how problem solving	Knowledge	3	<u>Basic understanding of climate change science</u>
1.3.	Climate Change	Know-how problem solving	Skills	3	Identifies useful and missing data, can foresee the trends from data
					What does it mean to identify useful data?
					A) Finding data that is easy to collect
					B) Finding data that is relevant and can provide valuable insights

					C) Finding data that is hard to understand
					D) Finding data that is not important
					Answer: B
					Which of the following is an example of foreseeing trends from data?
					A) Predicting future sales based on past data
					B) Ignoring past data
					C) Assuming data is incorrect without analysis
					D) Not using any data for decision-making
					Answer: A
2.1.	Climate Change	Climate Change Cross-cultural practice	Knowledge	3	Understanding that the security of the environment should be a personal goal
2.1.	Climate Change	Climate Change Cross-cultural practice	Skills	3	Can identify different national and international regulations to mitigate climate change
2.1.	Climate Change	Climate Change Cross-cultural practice	Skills	3	Works alone and cooperates to reduce gas emissions, air and water pollution
					How can individuals work alone to reduce air pollution?
					A) By increasing gas emissions
					B) By driving a car less frequently
					C) By ignoring pollution
					D) By using more plastic

					Answer: B
					How can individuals work together to reduce water pollution?
					A) By dumping waste into water bodies
					B) By using less water
					C) By properly disposing of waste and avoiding harmful chemicals
					D) By ignoring pollution prevention measures
					Answer: C
2.2.	Climate Change	Collaboration among diverse stakeholders	Knowledge	3	Understands that collaborations can be created with potential long-term benefits including ensuring the cost-effectiveness of planned actions, and helping to address and resolve competing priorities
2.2.	Climate Change	Collaboration among diverse stakeholders	Skills	3	Gets involved in a non-profit organisation
					How can collaboration help address and resolve competing priorities?
					A) By ignoring competing priorities
					B) By bringing together stakeholders to find common ground and solutions
					C) By creating more competing priorities
					D) By avoiding discussions about priorities
					Answer: B
					How can individuals contribute to collaborations for long-term benefits?

					A) By working alone and not collaborating with others
					B) By actively participating in discussions, sharing ideas, and working towards common goals
					C) By avoiding collaboration
					D) By creating more competing priorities
					Answer: B
2.3.	Climate Change	Climate informed change management	Knowledge	3	Understanding that society must adapt to a changed climate
2.3.	Climate Change	Climate informed change management	Skills	3	Shows personally adapted and changed personal lifestyle for climate change
3.1.	Climate Change	Climate change communication	Knowledge	3	Has different level of knowledge: economic, political, scientific to communicate the climate change
3.1.	Climate Change	Climate change communication	Skills	3	Developed ability to tackle the climate change calls for bridging the science/policy/civil society gap
					What does it mean to bridge the science/policy/civil society gap?
					A) To widen the gap between these sectors
					B) To ignore the gaps between these sectors
					C) To bring together science, policy, and civil society to collaborate and address climate change effectively

					D) To avoid collaboration between these sectors
					Answer: C
					How can individuals communicate climate change effectively to different audiences?
					A) By using complex scientific jargon
					B) By simplifying the information and using language that resonates with the audience's values and interests
					C) By avoiding communication
					D) By ignoring different audiences
					Answer: B
3.2.	Climate Change	Various scientific areas and industrial cross-sector cooperation	Knowledge	3	Understands the scientific and industry cooperation importance
3.2.	Climate Change	Various scientific areas and industrial cross-sector cooperation	Skills	3	Is able to tackle the issues and barriers occurring in the cross-industry cooperation process for climate change
					What are some issues and barriers that may occur in cross-industry cooperation for climate change?
					A) Lack of communication and trust between industries
					B) Excessive collaboration
					C) Ignoring climate change
					D) Increasing greenhouse gas emissions

					Answer: A
					How can scientific cooperation contribute to addressing climate change?
					A) By avoiding collaboration with industry
					B) By conducting research, providing data and evidence, and informing policy and industry actions
					C) By increasing pollution
					D) By ignoring climate change
					Answer: B
4.3.	Climate Change	Risk Management, Vulnerability & Impact Analysis	Skills	3	Climatic and non-climatic issues and stresses environmental change and consumption levels, and their integration with other drivers
					What are non-climatic issues related to environmental change?
					A) Issues unrelated to the environment
					B) Issues related to human activities, such as deforestation and pollution
					C) Issues related to animals
					D) Issues related to technology
					Answer: B
					How can consumption levels affect environmental change?
					A) Higher consumption levels lead to lower environmental impact

					B) Higher consumption levels lead to higher environmental impact
					C) Consumption levels have no impact on the environment
					D) Consumption levels only affect the climate
					Answer: B
5.1.	Climate Change	Prevention and preparedness actions	Skills	3	Community based disaster preparedness and mitigation programmes
6.1.	Climate Change	Adaptation knowledge creation	Knowledge	3	Mitigation efforts to lower greenhouse gas emissions
6.2.	Climate Change	Monitoring the speed of phenomena and their adaption	Knowledge	3	Conceptual background of approaches to address loss and damage associated with slow onset events
					How can individuals and communities prepare for slow onset events?
					A) By ignoring the events
					B) By implementing adaptation measures, such as sustainable land management and coastal protection
					C) By increasing consumption levels
					D) By avoiding collaboration
					Answer: B

					What is the role of governments and organisations in addressing loss and damage associated with slow onset events?
					A) They have no role in addressing loss and damage
					B) They play a key role in implementing policies and strategies to reduce vulnerability and enhance resilience
					C) They increase vulnerability
					D) They ignore the events
					Answer: B
7.1. Climate Change	Macro fiscal policy dedicated to climate change	Knowledge	3		Climate change mitigation requires a transition in the structure of economic activity on a massive scale
					How can individuals and businesses contribute to the transition in economic activity for climate change mitigation?
					A) By increasing reliance on fossil fuels
					B) By adopting sustainable practices, reducing energy consumption, and investing in renewable energy
					C) By ignoring climate change
					D) By increasing pollution
					Answer: B
					What role do governments play in facilitating the transition in economic activity for climate change mitigation?
					A) They play no role in facilitating the transition

					B) They implement policies and regulations to incentivize sustainable practices, promote renewable energy, and reduce emissions
					C) They increase reliance on fossil fuels
					D) They ignore climate change
					Answer: B
EQF level 4					
1.2.	Climate Change	Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy	Knowledge	4	Understanding of the practical characteristic features of climate change as a form of human knowledge and inquiry
1.2.	Climate Change	Climate Change Adaptation Practice Literacy	Skills	4	Support the use of factual information and rational explanations and express the need for logical and careful processes in drawing conclusions
					What role does scientific inquiry play in understanding climate change?
					A) It has no role in understanding climate change
					B) It helps gather evidence, analyse data, and draw conclusions based on factual information and logical reasoning
					C) It increases confusion
					D) It ignores climate change
					Answer: B
					How can individuals support the use of factual information and rational explanations in discussions about climate change?

					A) By avoiding discussions
					B) By promoting critical thinking, scientific literacy, and evidence-based decision-making
					C) By ignoring scientific evidence
					D) By using logical fallacies
					Answer: B
1.3.	Climate Change	Know-how problem solving	Knowledge	4	Understanding of scientific consensus on climate change and potential impacts
1.3.	Climate Change	Know-how problem solving	Skills	4	Highlights key problem/solution components, suggests concrete, original, and effective solutions spontaneously
					What are key problems/solutions components of climate change?
					A) Ignoring climate change
					B) Identifying the causes and impacts of climate change and developing mitigation and adaptation strategies
					C) Increasing greenhouse gas emissions
					D) Avoiding scientific consensus
					Answer: B
					How can individuals suggest concrete, original, and effective solutions to climate change spontaneously?
					A) By ignoring the issue
					B) By staying informed, thinking critically, and proposing innovative ideas and actions
					C) By avoiding scientific evidence
					D) By disregarding potential impacts

					Answer: B
2.1.	Climate Change	Climate Change Cross-cultural practice	Knowledge	4	Understanding that for cross-cultural collaboration the psychological barriers must be reduced (e.g. distrust, belief in external control, individualism-collectivism)
2.1.	Climate Change	Climate Change Cross-cultural practice	Skills	4	Is able to discuss scientific consensus with people who hold diverse beliefs about climate change
					How can individuals reduce psychological barriers for cross-cultural collaboration?
					A) By increasing distrust
					B) By building trust, promoting open communication, and understanding cultural differences
					C) By avoiding cultural differences
					D) By promoting individualism
					Answer: B
					How can individuals discuss scientific consensus with people who hold diverse beliefs about climate change?
					A) By avoiding discussions
					B) By engaging in respectful and constructive dialogues, presenting factual information, and addressing concerns and misconceptions
					C) By increasing distrust
					D) By ignoring diverse beliefs
					Answer: B

	Climate Change	Collaboration among diverse stakeholders	Knowledge	4	Understands that private companies can provide technological solutions and make them more affordable for resolving problems
					Why is it important for private companies to make technological solutions more affordable?
					A) To increase profits
					B) To ensure widespread adoption and impact of the technologies
					C) To increase costs
					D) To avoid collaboration
					Answer: B
	Climate Change	Climate informed change management	Knowledge	4	Understands the appropriate use of system tools such as biodiversity assessments and product life-cycle assessments
	Climate Change	Climate informed change management	Skills	4	Advocates for the appropriate use of system tools such as biodiversity assessments and product life-cycle assessments
	Climate Change	Climate informed change management	Skills	4	Evaluates risks in the enterprise
					Why is it important for private companies to make technological solutions more affordable?
					A) To increase profits
					B) To ensure widespread adoption and impact of the technologies

					C) To increase costs
					D) To avoid collaboration
					Answer: B
					What are product life-cycle assessments (LCAs) used for?
					A) To increase pollution
					B) To assess the environmental impacts of a product throughout its entire life cycle, from raw material extraction to disposal
					C) To avoid environmental impacts
					D) To ignore product impacts
					Answer: B
					Why is it important to advocate for the appropriate use of biodiversity assessments and LCAs?
					A) To increase biodiversity loss
					B) To ensure that decisions and policies are based on accurate and comprehensive information about biodiversity and product impacts
					C) To ignore biodiversity and product impacts
					D) To avoid using biodiversity and product impacts
					Answer: B
3.1.	Climate Change	Climate change communication	Knowledge	4	Has enough scientific knowledge to convince the climate change deniers
3.1.	Climate Change	Climate change communication	Skills	4	Ability to gather data for effective interdisciplinary communication

					What are some strategies for gathering data for effective interdisciplinary communication?
					A) By avoiding data collection
					B) By conducting comprehensive literature reviews, collaborating with experts from different fields, and using appropriate methods and tools for data collection and analysis
					C) By increasing confusion
					D) By avoiding interdisciplinary collaboration
					Answer: B
					How can individuals use scientific knowledge to convince climate change deniers?
					A) By ignoring deniers
					B) By presenting clear, concise, and compelling scientific evidence, addressing misconceptions, and promoting open dialogue and understanding
					C) By increasing confusion
					D) By avoiding discussions with deniers
					Answer: B
3.2.	Climate Change	Various scientific areas and industrial cross-sector cooperation	Knowledge	4	Is informed what technologies and different areas knowledge and practice can be useful for climate change action
3.2.	Climate Change	Various scientific areas and industrial	Skills	4	Is able to reach an agreement between conflicting parts and offer alternative solutions

		cross-sector cooperation			
					What technologies can be useful for climate change action?
					A) Technologies that increase greenhouse gas emissions
					B) Technologies that promote renewable energy, energy efficiency, sustainable transportation, and waste management
					C) Technologies that ignore climate change
					D) Technologies that avoid collaboration
					Answer: B
					Why is it important to be informed about technologies for climate change action?
					A) To increase confusion
					B) To identify and implement effective solutions to mitigate and adapt to climate change
					C) To ignore climate change
					D) To avoid using technologies
					Answer: B
4.1.	Climate Change	Strategy & Planning for an adaptation	Knowledge	4	Environmental sensors
5.1.	Climate Change	Prevention and preparedness actions	Knowledge	4	Technologies for first responders

5.1.	Climate Change	Prevention and preparedness actions	Skills	4	Assess the Future Impact of Climatic Changes upon the Frequency and Severity of Disasters and the Implications for first response and Preparedness
					Why is it important to understand technologies for first responders?
					A) To increase disaster risks
					B) To improve the effectiveness, efficiency, and safety of first responders in emergency situations
					C) To ignore disasters
					D) To avoid using technologies
					Answer: B
					How can individuals assess the future impact of climatic changes on the frequency and severity of disasters?
					A) By increasing disaster risks
					B) By analysing climate change projections, historical data on disasters, and vulnerability assessments to predict future trends and inform preparedness and response efforts
					C) By ignoring disasters
					D) By avoiding collaboration
					Answer: B
5.2.	Climate Change	Resilience technologies, managing the consequences	Knowledge	4	Scientific breakthroughs in various domains ranging from technologies, solutions and services: drought-resilient crops, water saving technologies, satellites for environmental observation, rapid progress in adaptation science and climate analytics as a basis for state-of-the-art climate information, scaling up of digital tools to take our adaptive capacities to the next level

					How can satellites be used for environmental observation?
					A) By ignoring environmental changes
					B) By monitoring changes in the Earth's atmosphere, land, and oceans, providing valuable data for climate research, disaster response, and natural resource management
					C) By increasing environmental damage
					D) By avoiding using satellites
					Answer: B
					How can digital tools help scale up adaptive capacities?
					A) By avoiding digital tools
					B) By providing innovative solutions, facilitating data collection and analysis, and enhancing communication and decision-making for climate adaptation
					C) By increasing complexity
					D) By ignoring adaptive capacities
					Answer: B
6.1.	Climate Change	Adaptation knowledge creation	Knowledge	4	Adjust societies to withstand the impacts of climate change
					How can individuals contribute to adjusting societies to withstand climate change impacts?
					A) By ignoring climate change impacts

					B) By advocating for and supporting policies and initiatives that promote resilience, sustainable development, and adaptation to climate change
					C) By increasing vulnerability
					D) By avoiding societal adjustments
					Answer: B
6.2.	Climate Change	Monitoring the speed of phenomena and their adaption	Knowledge	4	Empirical evidence linking a cluster of slow onset events to human mobility decisions, trajectories and outcomes
					How can slow onset events impact human mobility?
					A) By increasing human mobility
					B) By influencing decisions to migrate, displacement patterns, and outcomes for affected populations
					C) By ignoring human mobility
					D) By avoiding human mobility decisions
					Answer: B
					What is empirical evidence?
					A) Evidence based on theory
					B) Evidence based on observation and experience
					C) Evidence that is ignored
					D) Evidence that avoids collaboration
					Answer: B
					EQF level 5

3.2.	Climate Change	Various scientific areas and industrial cross-sector cooperation	Knowledge	5	Is informed that climate change reduction is not only a scientific problem, but also of social sciences and humanities
					What role do social sciences play in addressing climate change?
					A) Social sciences increase climate change impacts
					B) Social sciences provide insights into human behaviour, societal structures, policy-making, and communication strategies that are essential for effective climate change mitigation and adaptation
					C) Social sciences ignore climate change
					D) Social sciences avoid collaboration
					Answer: B
4.1.	Climate Change	Strategy & Planning for an adaptation	Knowledge	5	Remote-sensing platforms
					How can remote-sensing platforms contribute to disaster response and management?
					A) By avoiding disaster response
					B) By providing real-time imagery and data on disaster-affected areas, helping emergency responders assess the situation, plan rescue operations, and monitor recovery efforts
					C) By increasing disaster response
					D) By ignoring data collection

					Answer: B
					Why are remote-sensing platforms important in scientific research and decision-making?
					A) Because they complicate data collection
					B) Because they provide timely, accurate, and comprehensive data for a wide range of applications, including environmental monitoring, agriculture, urban planning, and natural resource management
					C) Because they avoid data collection
					D) Because they increase data collection
					Answer: B

2.7. Climathon Use Case in practice: two case studies

The Climathon Use Case presents two performed activities related to Climate Change approaching two different levels of education:

- Secondary Education
- Higher Education institution

The structure of the HEI workshop participants was remarkably diverse from secondary education, encompassing a range of disciplines, including graphical information systems, environmental science, ecology, geosciences, psychology, physics, climatology, machine learning, geoinformatics, and geography. This diversity has significant implications for climate change communication, as it facilitates the interdisciplinary collaboration essential to address the complexity of climate change challenges.

2.7.1. Secondary Education

Context

The Climathon activity was originally a climate data analysis course designed for HEIs participants. The format and content were changed for implementation at secondary education institutions (more breaks for teachers to interact with participants) to accommodate the participants.

The primary educational impetus is to teach young participants the need for systematic tools of a quantitative approach to climate and data analysis. This is to meet the future challenges associated with anthropogenically enhanced climate warming within the context of the European Green Deal.

The Climathon occurred jointly from 11 to 13 October 2023 at the Gymnasium Smart (RGSMART) in Novi Sad, Serbia, and the primary school Ellinogermaniki Agogi (EA) in Athens, Greece.

Use Target

Climathon participants were recruited based on their interest in climate-related topics. Students in the 9th and 10th grades were invited to participate in their overall Climate Change projects piloted during the school year (e.g., skills labs and science clubs).

User Involvement

A total of 25 pupils participated in the Climathon, 20 from RGSMART and five from EA. The RGSMART pupils came from two educational modules: general education and informatics. This meant that, in addition to a broad general education, they also focused on mathematics and physics in their education. The pupils from EA were 9th and 10th graders. At the Serbian site, the pupils were supervised by the school director Jelena Desnica (RGSMART), the local teacher Aleksandar Radišić (RGSMART) and the researcher Biljana Basarin (UNSPMF). In contrast, at the Greece site, the pupils were supervised by the local teacher, Loukas Katikas (EA).

Implementation Schedule

The schedule for this activity was as follows:

Day 1, Wednesday, 11. October 2023	
Time	Description
08.30– 09.00	Technical preparations at CRA, EA and RGSMART
09.00– 09.15	Welcome, presentation of course developer and lecturer Dr. Manfred Mudelsee (CRA) as well of local teacher Aleksandar Radisic (RGSMART) and representatives Biljana Basarin (UNSPMF) and Jelena Desnica (RGSMART)
09.15– 10.00	Lecture: Climate. climate system; climate variables (temperature, precipitation, wind speed); surface-air temperature time series, global; surface-air temperature time series, local (Potsdam, Germany); paleoclimate rainfall time series; proxy variables

10.00– 10.15	Break
10.15– 11.00	Lecture: Climate (continued). climate equation; trend component; extreme component; noise component; scientific method; Karl Popper; Plato; first principles of physics; statistical inference
11.00– 11.15	Break
11.15– 12.00	Exercises. How do the first principles of physics lead to the climate equation or something else? What is a 90% confidence band? Do you have examples of concepts for complex systems other than climate?
Day 2, Thursday, 12. October 2023	
Time	Description
08.55– 09.00	Technical preparations at CRA, EA and GSMART
09.00– 09.45	Lecture: Climate Data. Temperature time series; measurement devices; invention of thermometer; daily measurement practices
09.45– 10.15	Break
10.15– 11.00	Lecture: Climate Data (continued). Mean monthly versus mean monthly temperature time series; sample size; leap days; GISTEMP global, monthly-mean, surface-air temperature time series
11.00– 11.15	Break
11.15– 12.00	Exercises. How many days comprise the time interval from 01/01/1893 to 31/12/2018? Data homogeneity: rural versus urban temperature measurement stations. Data file and text editor. Find the Internet's temperature data for your preferred station (town).
Day 3, Friday, 13. October 2023	
Time	Description
08.55– 09.00	Technical preparations at CRA, EA and GSMART
09.00– 09.45	Lecture: Climate Data Analysis. Trend component definition; linear trend model. How do we infer linear trend components? Uncertainties.
09.45– 10.15	Break
10.15– 11.00	Lecture: Climate Data (continued). Statistical inference. The idea of least-squares trend estimation. Calculation of least squares trend estimates for the GISTEMP series.
11.00– 11.15	Break
11.15– 12.00	Exercises. Software LINFIT. Replication of calculation of least squares trend estimates for the GISTEMP series. Calculation of least squares trend estimates for the series from the preferred stations (Day 2). Discussion: Nonlinear trend models.
12.00	Farewell

Curriculum

The Climathon activity is linked to the high school curriculum since it integrates relevant material into existing subjects via interdisciplinary activities. Subjects such as science and skills labs and extracurricular activities such as TEDx and Young Scientists Groups lend themselves to projects and discussions on climate change and climate data analysis that allow students to be introduced to more complex scientific topics.

Assessment

Before the Climathon course, pupils' knowledge about climate varied. Some had a basic understanding of climate and its relationship to geographical location, while others were aware of global warming. However, many admitted to knowing very little or nothing at all. After the Climathon course, participants gained a deeper

understanding of the climate. They learned about the long-term weather patterns, the significant changes in climate, the complexity of the climate system, and the impact of carbon dioxide emissions on climate change. They also learned how to analyse primary climate data.

2.7.2. Higher Education institution

Context

The Climathon activity supported the development of competencies. It raised awareness regarding the adaptation to climate change and the methodological tools needed to analyse the challenges using the vast amount of available data. Climathon focused on organising activities such as practical training and (online) climate time series analysis courses. The course was based on the book *Climate Time Series Analysis: Classical Statistical and Bootstrap Methods*, 2nd edition, authored by CRA's CEO Dr. Manfred Mudelsee and published by Springer in 2014.

The Climathon occurred at the University of Novi Sad, Serbia, within the Faculty of Sciences (UNSPMF) and its Department of Geography, Tourism, and Hotel Management, on 6 and 7 March 2024. The event seamlessly integrated physical and virtual participation using a hybrid approach.

User Target

Climathon participants were recruited based on their interest in climate-related topics. Students from the geography, physics, meteorology, environmental studies, and geosciences MSc and PhD level study programs were invited to participate in their overall climate change projects piloted during the spring semester.

User Involvement

The event seamlessly integrated physical and virtual participation using a hybrid approach. A total of 27 students participated in the Climathon, demonstrating a commendable commitment to advancing their understanding of climate dynamics. Twenty-four of them were undergraduates, while there was one master's student and two PhD candidates, collectively reflecting a diverse range of academic pursuits and levels of expertise. UNSPMF researchers facilitated the course implementation, and CRA researchers delivered the course.

Curriculum

At UNSPMF, the Climathon activity is linked to the BSc study program in geography (G104 Climatology with the basis of meteorology, DG302 Global Climate Change, G102 Mathematical Geography with basics of Astronomy, G206 Environmental Geography), MSc study program in geography (MGI501 Methods for the analysis of geographic data), PhD study program in geography (DRG101 Global climate changes and water management, DGT102 Mathematic and statistical research methods in geography and tourism, DRG111 Environment, Planning and Geoecology).

Assessment

After the Climathon, students were given a short voluntary online survey to assess their knowledge before and after the course. Before participating in the Climathon course, the students had varying levels of knowledge about climate change, with some having a basic understanding from school and others being aware of the current state of climate change globally. However, their knowledge was generally limited to basic concepts. After completing the course, students reported a significant increase in their understanding of climate change, gaining insights into its significance, the mechanisms for coping with its impacts and the complexity of its interconnected systems. The course also stimulated a desire for further learning, particularly in climate science and renewable energy.

Cross-Cultural Impact

The following cultures or sectoral areas came together in the implementation of the demonstrator activity at the pilot site:

(1) industry and SME Owner (CRA) (Demonstrator),

- (2) head of school (RGSMART), teacher (RGSMART), university support (UNSPMF) (Pilot),
- (3) pupils at secondary education institutions (Participants).

The objective shows the success of the implementation. This is supported on a more subjective basis, as those responsible for the demonstrator and pilot activities (numbers (1) and (2) above), who shared their experiences after the event, felt that the participants were engaged and present until the end of the activity.

A notable support to pilot partner RGSMART was the presence of University Professor Biljana Basarin (UNSPMF) during the pilot implementation, facilitated by the fact that both partner institutions are located in the same city (Novi Sad, Serbia).

Regarding the “other direction,” the demonstrator and pilot activity leaders also confirmed that the implementation of the activity contributed to the training of the teachers and activity developers.

Conclusion

Overall, the Climathon course provided participants from higher education with valuable insights into the importance and techniques of climate data analysis, enabling them to use data to address climate change challenges effectively. Before the Climathon course, there needed to be more knowledge of climate data analysis.

Some needed more understanding, such as annual data statistics published by relevant organisations. However, the majority expressed a need for more knowledge about data analysis techniques and their applications in the context of climate data. Participants reported significant progress in understanding climate data analysis after completing the course. They learned about the importance of analysis methods, how to extract and analyse data, and their practical utility in identifying trends, patterns, and anomalies. Many participants also mentioned an increased desire to learn more in this area.

Most pupils needed more understanding of climate data analysis before the Climathon course. While some may have recognised its general importance or the use of graphs, they needed to gain knowledge of the specific methods and techniques used by scientists. After the course, there was a marked improvement. Participants learned how scientists analyse climate data, use tools such as Excel for visualisation, interpret the results to understand patterns of climate change, and even appreciate the complexity of turning raw data into meaningful insights.

The simplicity of the questions in the assessment tool meant that participants were probably willing to answer more honestly than long questionnaires. On the other hand, we cannot rule out the possibility that these data show a degree of censorship (i.e., missing “negative” responses) due to voluntary participation in the assessment. As our interpretation of the responses is qualitative, we do not feel censored data tools are justified.

The simplicity of the assessment tool, in combination with the clarity of the results, means that there is an overall robust finding, namely that our teaching was successful, and there was an increase in knowledge about climate, climate data, and climate data analysis achieved both by participants from the higher and the secondary education levels. Nevertheless, an event as short as two or three days for the Climathons cannot replace a semester-long weekly lecture or a two-week-long daily computer course. However, we are optimistic that the issues of global climate change and the European Green Deal, which were implicitly present during the entire events and were also often explicitly mentioned during the events, will stay as application fields that have high socioeconomic relevance and deserve future attention and can be tackled quantitatively through climate data analysis.

Over the coming decades, climate action (SDG 13) must adopt a dual strategy of mitigation and adaptation to address the enormous threats to humans and other life on Earth, as is set out, for example, in the ambitious targets of the European Green Deal. Quality education (SDG 4) in quantitative, data-driven scientific approaches can help shape the next generation of responsible scientists. Quality online education has been boosted in the years since the COVID-19 pandemic.

Because of its electronic nature, this approach is driven by theory, facts, and data. Therefore, it contributes to the “rational aspects” of climate change research.

The two Climathons described in this article were successful as online educational activities for higher and secondary education participants, as documented by the evaluation (Table 9.1). These successes can also be achieved in specific other dimensions. More extended educational series can lead to more profound learning experiences in the time dimension. Regarding space, audiences in different parts of Europe or the world can be addressed if a caring attitude is maintained, with local teachers or experts offering help and explanations. Finally, climate change is a multidisciplinary field of research, and the educational concept of our Climathons should also apply to other disciplines involved, such as ecology, econometrics, environmental sciences, geosciences, hydrology, meteorology, computer science, chemistry, or physics.

Are there limits to the rational, online nature of the course? Yes, the face-to-face contact between student and teacher is essential to complete the training, as it trains young researchers' intuition. In a certain sense, the meetings must be on an equal footing to not violate both sides' integrity since the teacher may have more knowledge at the beginning. An open mind and a willingness to learn from mistakes and criticism (Popper, 1959) are more critical today than ever.

3. References

- Cenozoic CO₂ Proxy Integration Project (CenCO₂PIP) Consortium. (2023). Toward a Cenozoic history of atmospheric CO₂. *Science* 382, eadi5177. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adi5177>
- IPCC. (2021). *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Working Group I Contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.* V. Masson-Delmotte, P. Zhai, A. Pirani, S. L. Connors, C. Péan, Y. Chen, L. Goldfarb, M. I. Gomis, J. B. R. Matthews, S. Berger, M. Huang, O. Yelekçi, R. Yu & B. Zhou (Eds.), (Vols. 1–2). Cambridge Univ. Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157896>
- International Organization for Standardization. (2012). *Conformity assessment — General requirements for bodies operating certification of persons (ISO/IEC 17024:2012).* <https://www.iso.org/standard/52993.html>
- Lüthi, D., Le Floch, M., Bereiter, B., Blunier, T., Barnola, J.-M., Siegenthaler, U., Raynaud, D., Jouzel, J., Fischer, H., Kawamura, K., & Stocker, T. F. (2008). High-resolution carbon dioxide concentration record 650,000–800,000 years before present. *Nature* 453(7193), 379–382.
- Mudelsee, M. (2014). *Climate Time Series Analysis. Second Edition.* Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-04450-7>
- Mudelsee, M. (2020). *Statistical Analysis of Climate Extremes.* Cambridge Univ. Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781139519441>
- Popper, K. R. (1959). *The Logic of Scientific Discovery.* Basic Books.